

HEAVY METALS IN MOSSES IN AREAS ADJACENT TO ZINC AND LEAD SMELTERS IN MIASTECZKO ŚLĄSKIE AND BUKOWNO

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Introduction

Bioindication of the environment with mosses is a good, reliable and widely used method. Mosses (because of their anatomical structure) are deriving metals mainly from atmospheric deposits – wet and dry. Mosses have high capacity to retain plenty of. Because they have no roots the contribution of heavy metals from the soil solution in their tissue could be omitted [KUIK, WOLTERBEEK 1995]. TYLER [1990] have found that the concentration of such elements as: Cd, Ni, Cu, Pb and Fe in mosses correlated with their concentration in precipitation ($r=0.95$). The best species for monitoring purposes are epigeic, carpet forming mosses e.g. *Pleurozium schreberi* (Brid.), *Hylocomium splendens* (Hedw.), *Polytrichum formosum* (Hedw.) and others.

The purpose of present were:

- to investigate the impact of non - ferrous smelter on the environment with mosses as bioindicators;
- to study if bioindication with mosses is a good method in the surrounding of zinc and lead smelter.

Material and methods

Mosses: *Pleurozium schreberi*, *Sphagnum* sp., *Mnium* sp., *Polytrichum formosum* and *Hylocomium splendens* were collected in 8 points around two great zinc and lead smelters in Upper Silesian Industrial Region (Southern Poland):

- „Miasteczko Śląskie” situated 50°27` N; 18°52` E, and
- „Bolesław” situated 50°17` N; 19°27` E.

Plants were collected in distance up to 3 km from the emitters. The investigated area covers about 128 km². Mosses in all those area were found very rarely.

In Miasteczko Śląskie there were collected only 7 samples of *Pleurozium schreberi*, 3 samples of *Sphagnum* sp., 1 sample of *Mnium* sp., 1 sample of *Hylocomium splendens* and *Polytrichum formosum*. The situation in Bolesław was even worse. There were collected 5 samples of *Pleurozium schreberi* and 1 sample of *Mnium* sp.

A reference material was collected from Białowieża Primeval Forest (52° 40' N; 23°50' E); about 600 km NE of Upper Silesian Industrial Region. The Białowieża could be considered as „clean” from industrial pollution.

Mosses collected near the smelters were carefully sorted by hands and only green parts were used for analysis. Plants were washed in tap and distilled water, dried in 105°C and grounded to a powder and then „dry” mineralized in 460°C. The ash was digested in HNO₃. Each sample (5 g) was tripled and the results are arithmetical means of 3 repetitions. The concentration of Zn, Pb, Cd, Fe, Cu and Mn were measured using conventional AAS method. Quality of analytical procedures were controlled by using internal samples with known Values.

Results and discussion

The concentration of investigated elements (except Mn) in moss samples were approximately 3 folds higher near both smelters than in uncontaminated place in Białowieża (Fig. 1–5).

Fig. 1. Mean concentration of some heavy metals in moss *Pleurozium schreberi* (µg·g⁻¹ DM)

Rys. 1. Średnia zawartość metali ciężkich w mchu *Pleurozium schreberi* (µg·g⁻¹ s.m.)

Sphagnum sp., *Polytrichum formosum* were not found in the distance 3 km from the zinc and lead smelter in Bukowno. Such results are probably due to the pollution from the zinc and lead processing plants. Content of manganese in mosses were 1.4–1.8 times higher in Białowieża than in plants collected near the smelters.

Fig. 2. Mean concentration of some heavy metals in moss *Mnium* sp. ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ DM)
 Rys. 2. Średnia zawartość metali ciężkich w mchu *Mnium* sp. ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ s.m.)

Fig. 3. Mean concentration of some heavy metals in moss *Sphagnum* sp. ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ DM)
 Rys. 3. Średnia zawartość metali ciężkich w mchu *Sphagnum* sp. ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ s.m.)

Fig. 4. Mean concentration of some heavy metals in moss *Polytrichum formosum* ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ DM)
 Rys. 4. Średnia zawartość metali ciężkich w mchu *Polytrichum formosum* ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ s.m.)

Fig. 5. Mean concentration of some heavy metals in moss *Hylocomium splendens* ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ DM)

Rys. 5. Średnia zawartość metali ciężkich w mchu *Hylocomium splendens* ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ DM)

Obtained results are generally in range reported in mosses from Poland and other countries. However in some cases (lead, cadmium in *Mnium* sp.) were higher than measured in other moss samples. (Tab. 1).

Table 1; Tabela 1

Concentrations of some elements in moss species ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$)
 Data cited after: REJMENT-GROCHOWSKA [1976]; PAKARINEN, RINNE [1979];
 RINNE BARCLAY-ESTRUP [1980]; GRODZIŃSKA [1989]; STEINESS et al. [1994];
 BARGALI et al. [1995]; KUIK, WOLTERBEEK [1995]

Zawartość metali w mchach ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$)
 Dane cytowane za: REJMENT-GROCHOWSKA [1976]; PAKARINEN, RINNE [1979];
 RINNE BARCLAY-ESTRUP [1980]; GRODZIŃSKA [1989]; STEINESS i in. [1994];
 BARGALI i in. [1995]; KUIK, WOLTERBEEK [1995]

Metals Metal	Concentration of metals in mosses Europe and North America Zawartość metali w mchach w Europie i Płn. Ameryce	Concentration of metals in mosses Poland Zawartość metali w mchach w Polsce
Zinc; Zn	40–1670	123–452
Lead; Pb	5–400	11–69
Cadmium; Cd	0.06–36.7	0.79–3.99
Iron; Fe	131–18500	391–742
Copper; Cu	6–197	0.8–4
Manganese; Mg	38–790	–

In plant material from „Miasteczko Śląskie” the greatest concentration of investigated metals were found in *Mnium* sp., but around „Bolesław” the greatest load of metals were found in *Pleurozium schreberi*.

Mosses are assumed to be suitable stress bioindicators and the method of bioindication with mosses is recommended both for a large (geographical) scale surveys and local environment monitoring [JĘDRZEJKO 1990; RUCHLING et al. 1992;

GRODZIŃSKA et al. 1994; KUIK, WOLTERBEK 1995; MARKERT et al. 1996]. But the pollution of investigated area is so heavy, mosses around both zinc and lead smelters, are rarely found, even in such ecosystems where they should grow in great amount e.g. in pine forest around „Miasteczko Śląskie”.

It is because in so heavy polluted environment the mosses are dying [JĘDRZEJKO 1980]. As a consequence the number of samples which were found in the distance up to 3 km from emitters, were not enough to assess the contamination of the environment. There were not found any correlation between concentration of heavy metals in Miasteczko Śląskie, Bukowno and distance from the emitter. The correlation coefficient between concentration of heavy metals in plants and content of metals in dustfall [CIMANDER (Ed.) 1996] was statistically important (Miasteczko Śląskie $r=0.74$; Bukowno $r=0.92$).

It could be that in such polluted areas as near those two non ferrous metals smelters the method of bioindication with mosses was not so effective as it was when the objective was to assess the condition of larger area [RUHLING et al. 1992; GRODZIŃSKA et al. 1994; MARKERT et al. 1996].

Conclusions

Mosses from the surroundings of zinc and lead smelters in Upper Silesian Industrial Region were cumulating about 3 times higher amounts of Zn, Pb, Cd and Cu than same plants from unpolluted place in Białowieża Primeval Forest.

The bioindication with mosses near zinc and lead smelters was not enough to assess the condition of the environment, because in heavy polluted place the mosses were too rare. In such situation it is recommended to measure contamination of the soil by heavy metals simultaneously with bioindication with mosses.

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Key words: heavy metals, mosses, bioindication, zinc and lead smelter

Summary

Samples of mosses: *Pleurozium schreberi* (Brid.), *Polytrichum formosum* (Hedw.), *Hylocomium splendens* (Hedw.), *Sphagnum* sp. and *Mnium* sp. were collected within a radius of 3 km around lead and zinc smelters in Miasteczko Śląskie and Bukowno. The aim was to investigate contamination of the surroundings of the smelters with mosses as bioindicators. The content of heavy metals that was found in plants collected from the area neighbouring the non-ferrous metal smelters was higher than from non-polluted Białowieża Primeval Forest. The correlation coefficient of metal content in mosses and the distance from the smelter were not statistically significant. Such result was probably because of pollution of the atmosphere and the soil of Upper Silesian Industrial District. Within the distance of 3 km from the zinc and lead smelters the mosses (mainly *Hylocomium splendens* and *Pleurozium schreberi*) were growing to sparsely as for good bioindicators.

ZAWARTOŚĆ METALI CIĘŻKICH W MCHACH
WOKÓŁ HUT CYNKU I OŁOWIU
W MIASTECZKU ŚLĄSKIM I W BUKOWNIE

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Słowa kluczowe: metale ciężkie, mchy, bioindykacja, huta cynku i ołowiu

Streszczenie

Prowadzone badania miały na celu określenie stopnia skażenia środowiska przyrodniczego metalami ciężkimi (Zn, Pb, Cd, Fe, Cu i Mn) metodą bioindykacji z wykorzystaniem mchów. Mchy z gatunków: *Pleurozium schreberi* (Brid.), *Polytrichum formosum* (Hedw.), *Hylocomium splendens* (Hedw.), *Sphagnum* sp., and *Mnium* sp. zbierano w 3 km strefie wokół dwóch hut cynku i ołowiu w Miasteczku Śląskim i Bukownie oraz dodatkowo w Białowieży (jako obszaru względnie niezanieczyszczonego).

Zawartość metali ciężkich w roślinach pochodzących z obszarów sąsiadujących z hutami, była znacznie wyższa niż w roślinach pochodzących z Białowieży.

Nie stwierdzono istotnej statystycznie korelacji pomiędzy zawartością metali ciężkich w mchach a odległością od emitorów. Mchy na badanym terenie występowały rzadko, mimo sprzyjających warunków siedliskowych.

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